

Chemical Analysis of Some Wild Leguminous Seeds

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Preliminary examinations of the nutritional constituents of 6 wild leguminous seeds were studied. The chemical examination of wild leguminous seeds have been made for the isolation and characterisation of phospholipids constituents and the distribution of total nitrogen and dispersion of nitrogenous constituents in the various fractions of seeds are presented in this communication.

WITH a view to explore newer and effective sources of protein some wild uncultivated leguminous seeds of plants which grow profusely in country because of favourable soil and climate conditions^{1,2} have been studied. The seeds of leguminous plants constitute the chief source of proteins in the Indian diet^{3,4}. Faced with protein malnutrition caused by acute food shortage, researchers subjected some of these wild seeds to chemical analysis.

Though a lot of research work has been carried out in India and abroad on the different leguminous seeds, the present communication deals with a comparative chemical composition of six uncultivated leguminous seeds *Cassia fistula*, *C. multijuga*, *Trigonella occulta*, *Indigofera hirsuta*, *Indigofera glandulosa*, and *Indigofera trifoliata* of Bundelkhand region of Central India. The distribution of total nitrogen and the dispersion of nitrogenous constituents in the seeds of *Cassia fistula*, *Indigofera hirsuta*, *I. glandulosa* and *I. trifoliata* by employing different salts solutions at various concentrations were studied. Phospholipids constituents such as Cephalin and Lecithin ratio were also studied in the present communication.

Materials and Methods :

The experimental legumes were collected locally and from the different parts of Bundelkhand region in Central India and botanically identified. The seeds were cleaned and powdered in a grinder to 100 mesh, defatted with petroleum ether (60-80°). Moisture, ash, crude fibre and fat contents were determined according to the A.O.A.C. methods⁵. Nitrogen was determined by microkjeldahl method and from the results obtained, percentage of crude protein was calculated. Phosphorous and iron were estimated colorimetrically^{6,7}. Ethereal extractives were determined by usual methods.

Quantitative estimation of total soluble carbohydrate was carried out by the method of Trevelyan

and Harrison⁸. The method depends on the action of anthrone on carbohydrates producing characteristic colour.

Finally powdered seed was extracted with distilled water at room temperature. The mixture was centrifuged and the supernatant decanted. The residue was again stirred thoroughly with distilled water, centrifuged and the clear supernatant decanted. This process of extraction was repeated till the supernatant was negative to Molisch test. The combined supernatant was made up to 100 ml with distilled water. The working solution was prepared by diluting the extract (5 ml) with glass distilled water to 100 ml.

To the diluted extract (1 ml) in a stoppered tube, anthrone reagent (5 ml, 0.2% w/v) prepared in sulphuric acid (85%) was added, the contents of the tube well mixed and heated for 10 minutes in a boiling water bath. Optical density of the cooled solution was measured in a unicam S.P. 600 spectrophotometer at 620 m μ . The amount of total water soluble carbohydrate at room temperature was calculated from a calibration curve plotted earlier.

Fractionation of proteins from seeds were effected by the solubility method of Mitchell⁹. The defatted powder (12 gm) was successively extracted with water, sodium chloride solution (5% w/v), ethanol (75% v/v) and sodium hydroxide (0.25% w/v) until the extracts were negative to the biuret test. Non-protein nitrogen was estimated by employing trichloroacetic acid (2.5% w/v) as the protein precipitant. The detailed scheme of extraction and fractionation is represented schematically in figure 1.

Seed proteins were extracted with eight different solvents (copper sulphate, potassium chloride, bromide, iodide and sulphate and sodium chloride, sulphate and bicarbonate) of concentrations 0.25, 0.50 and 1.00 N. The defatted seed meals (4 gm) were extracted in duplicate with each of the extractants in 250 ml. Erlenmeyer flasks by shaking for

Figure 1. Fractionation chart.

2 hours in a mechanical shaker and then centrifuging for 15 minutes at 2500 r.p.m. The pH of the clear supernatant was measured in the Beckman pH meter. First, the pH meter is calibrated frequently by checking against a standard buffer of known pH, readjusting the scale setting if necessary. Now the extracted solution of seed is placed in a small container and the glass electrode and calomel electrode immersed in the solution. The potentiometer circuit is closed and adjusted until the null point is reached. The pH may then be read directly in pH meter and nitrogen was determined in 5 ml of each extract. From the total nitrogen of the defatted seed meals the per cent of nitrogen so extracted was calculated.

The phospholipids were extracted from the mixture of chloroform and methanol (2 : 1 v/v).

The seeds were powdered and extracted with a mixture of chloroform and methanol (2 : 1 v/v) in soxhlet assembly, the whole extract was distilled to small volume whereupon an oily mass was obtained. This oily extract along with 0.2% KCl solution was taken in a separating funnel and shaker to get separated lipid and non-lipid layer. The phospholipids were separated from other lipids by means of acetone. The phospholipids containing cephalin and lecithin were insoluble in acetone, they were separated from other lipids by acetone. The lecithin and cephalin were separated by means of column chromatography using silica gel G as absorbent and chloroform and methanol as solvents. The ratio of cephalin and lecithin were calculated in the seeds which were found to contain more percentage of cephalin and less percentage of lecithin.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that the wild inedible leguminous seeds contained the percentage of crude protein 22-31% which shows their possible inclusion in animal nutrition. The percentage of carbohydrate in the seeds are between 9.68 to 11.80%.

Table 2 indicates that successive extraction of

TABLE 2—DISTRIBUTION OF TOTAL NITROGEN IN THE SEEDS

Protein Fraction	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	<i>Indigofera hirsuta</i>	<i>Indigofera glandulosa</i>	<i>Indigofera trifoliata</i>
Water soluble (alb + globulin + NPN)	59.4 ± 1.8	57.3 ± 2.6	61.7 ± 3.15	63.1 ± 2.8
Globulin A	38.6 ± 2.15	35.4 ± 1.05	41.8 ± 2.25	36.5 ± 1.86
5% NaCl soluble (Globulin B)	17.8 ± 2.02	18.6 ± 1.8	20.7 ± 2.40	20.2 ± 1.60
Total globulin	56.4	54.0	62.5	56.7
NPN (Non-Protein nitrogen)	11.8 ± 2.30	14.4 ± 1.70	12.2 ± 2.15	13.2 ± 2.6
75% ethanol-soluble (Prolamine)	1.6 ± 0.25	4.6 ± 0.5	1.2 ± 0.30	2.7 ± 0.20
0.25% NaOH soluble (Glutelin)	9.8 ± 0.6	7.5 ± 1.05	11.2 ± 0.20	8.6 ± 0.16
Residue	5.8 ± 1.2	8.3 ± 0.8	7.2 ± 0.5	6.6 ± 0.65

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF SOME WILD LEGUMINOUS SEEDS. (DRY WEIGHT BASIS)

Constituents	Leguminous Seeds					
	<i>Cassia multijuga</i>	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	<i>Trigonella occulta</i>	<i>Indigofera hirsuta</i>	<i>Indigofera glandulosa</i>	<i>Indigofera trifoliata</i>
1. Moisture%	8.50	5.95	6.84	4.80	5.96	5.42
2. Ash%	3.50	3.00	3.80	3.96	2.22	3.24
3. Fat (ether-extractives)%	1.80	1.61	3.78	3.20	3.86	3.91
4. Crude protein (N × 6.25)%	27.62	31.00	24.80	22.56	25.80	24.62
5. Crude fibre%	8.40	13.08	9.06	10.20	9.60	9.90
6. Carbohydrate%	10.56	11.80	9.68	10.10	10.20	9.98
7. Minerals						
Iron (mg/100 gm)	81	78	109	63	66	64
8. Inorganic						
Phosphorous (mg/100 gm)	36	36	33	31	44	43

TABLE 3—EXTRACTION OF SEED PROTEINS BY SALT SOLUTIONS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS (MEAN OF DUPLICATE DETERMINATIONS)

Salt	Seed	Concentrations					
		0.25N		0.50N		1.0N	
		% of total N extracted	Resultant pH of extract	% total N extracted	Resultant pH of extract	% total N extracted	Resultant pH of extract
CuSO ₄	1	50.6	3.45	55.8	3.38	55.8	3.50
	2	52.7	3.46	53.5	3.40	56.6	3.28
	3	50.4	3.35	54.2	3.36	54.7	3.36
	4	48.8	3.40	53.8	3.40	53.2	3.32
NaCl	1	73.2	6.03	74.6	5.88	71.6	5.90
	2	78.00	6.10	70.5	6.10	75.0	5.92
	3	60.6	5.95	62.5	6.02	62.4	6.00
	4	65.2	6.15	66.4	5.88	68.3	5.95
KCl	1	60.8	6.12	72.5	6.10	71.5	5.95
	2	72.8	6.10	69.8	6.06	71.4	6.80
	3	70.4	6.14	75.6	6.15	74.3	5.90
	4	72.2	5.98	65.8	6.10	57.5	6.00
KBr	1	74.5	6.05	70.5	6.00	72.6	5.88
	2	72.6	5.84	76.5	6.10	75.6	5.95
	3	78.8	6.05	78.2	6.10	77.4	5.90
	4	76.4	6.05	72.8	6.10	72.2	5.89
KI	1	78.6	6.05	78.7	6.00	80.9	5.95
	2	78.0	6.07	75.3	6.05	79.9	5.94
	3	65.5	6.08	70.4	5.90	65.0	5.89
	4	64.6	6.04	67.3	6.06	67.4	6.00
NaHCO ₃	1	74.5	8.10	74.8	8.14	73.8	8.22
	2	76.5	8.20	76.6	8.25	75.3	8.35
	3	77.6	8.30	80.4	8.30	78.2	8.36
	4	72.8	8.32	71.5	8.28	74.5	8.21
Na ₂ SO ₄	1	68.4	5.86	68.3	5.90	69.4	5.82
	2	65.2	5.90	66.4	5.93	64.2	5.92
	3	67.4	6.00	65.7	5.94	60.2	5.95
	4	60.8	6.89	60.2	5.94	62.3	5.90
K ₂ SO ₄	1	65.3	5.60	63.4	5.88	65.0	5.95
	2	70.4	6.00	70.8	6.01	73.6	5.89
	3	66.4	6.05	67.8	6.07	68.5	5.98
	4	68.0	6.12	66.2	6.04	67.6	6.00

Seeds 1=*Cassia fistula*, 2=*Indigofera hirsuta*, 3=*I. glandulosa*, 4=*I. trifoliata*.

seeds with water and sodium chloride solubilizes 75 to 83% of the total nitrogen which consists of globulin, albumin and non-protein nitrogen of combined origin. Globulin constitutes the major fraction of total proteins of seeds and measures between 54 to 62% of the total nitrogen. Prolamin forms a small fraction 1 to 4% whereas non-protein nitrogen accounts for 11 to 14% and in residue remains unextracted nitrogen amounts to about 5 to 8%.

Table 3 shows the extraction of seed proteins by eight different salt solutions such as copper sulphate, sodium chloride, potassium chloride, bromide and iodide, sodium bicarbonates sulphate and potassium sulphate, at different concentrations. pH were measured at different concentrations of seed solutions in view of isolating proteins from the seeds.

Extraction of proteins by different salt solutions at various concentrations confirms the findings of Smith et al^{10,11} and Evans and Kerr¹². Observations of the inhibiting influence of the divalent Cu⁺² ions on the solubility of proteins is also in accord with the findings of Smith et al.

The seeds are richest source of phospholipids in plants. The seeds contain more amount of cephalin, 58 to 66% and less amount of lecithin 33 to 41%. This indicates that in the seeds of *Cassia fistula*, *Indigofera hirsuta* and *Indigofera trifoliata* the amount of lecithin and cephalin are present approximately in the ratio of 1:2 as shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4—RATIO OF CEPHALIN AND LECITHIN IN PHOSPHOLIPIDS

Seed	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	<i>Indigofera hirsuta</i>	<i>Indigofera glandulosa</i>	<i>Indigofera trifoliata</i>
Cephalin%	64.40	65.60	58.8	66.60
Lecithin%	35.60	34.40	41.2	33.40

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